

Building a Better Madhesh: Good Governance through Transparency, Accountability, and Prosperity

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Abstract

Good Governance is the polity that works for the maximum welfare of the citizens of a nation. All organs, departments and units under the Government initiate their action in the best interest of the native people. Also, the natural resources are at the disposal of all and sundry. Other features include transparency, accountability, mass participation, the rule of law, human rights, independent judiciary, inclusive development and keeping corruption in check. The political actors raise themselves above the triviality of the high and low, the rich and the poor, kith and kin, class and caste, religion and reason, language and culture in order to sincerely bring the nation to the path of progress and prosperity. Madhesh for its otherness has been exploited economically, politically, socially, culturally and in many other ways for centuries. It has borne the heavy yoke of the Ranas' and kings' rules. The country has now ushered in a republic; yet Madheshis suffer the same predicament. Madhesh meets the conditions of being a perfect province within Nepal. It has its own unique geography, history, culture, language and all that. It has been the international practice to recognize this kind of territory as a nation/state/province. A smaller country than Nepal, Switzerland has not less than 28 cantons and four official languages such as German, French, Italian and Romance based on different nationalities. The USA has fifty States; India has increased its number of States. The purpose of my research paper is to expose the hollowness of the ruling class as well as their ascendancy over the Madheshis. This paper also suggests measures to be taken for the amelioration of Madhesh. Different sources such as authentic books and own my knowledge and experience are the bases of my paper.

Keywords: polity, yoke, nation, nationality